

Research Article

Comparative Study of the Spawning Success of Goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) Using Synthetic Hormone and Natural Simulation

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Abstract

Practical studies to compare the efficiency of the synthetic hormone ovaprim on the spawning success of goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) with that of natural breeding was carried out using plastic tanks. The experiment was conducted in two different set up using two males and two females broodstocks. One male and one female were set up for the artificial breeding (ovaprim induced) and the other pair for the natural breeding. The weights of the fish were recorded as 25g, 27g for females and 20g for males. The ovaprim was injected into their body, for artificial breeding, at the rate of 0.5ml/kg body weight of the fish. After injecting the male and the female broodstock with ovaprim, they were left to spawn on their own in a prepared tank containing 20–50 liters of water with a floating plant. Hatching of the young ones occurred at 72 hours after spawning, at 27°C. The total numbers of eggs obtained by artificial and natural breeding were 350 and 220 eggs respectively. The hatchability was also found to be 99.56% for the artificial and 90.00% for natural breeding. The percentage survival rate of the fry was 86.0% for ovaprim and 68.3% for the natural breeding. It can, therefore, be deduced that artificial breeding conducted using ovaprim gives a better result than natural breeding and also has a greater survival rate.

Keywords: gold fish, ovaprim, natural breeding, synthetic hormone, hatchability, survival rate.

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Introduction

Aquarium keeping is becoming more popular and is the second-largest hobby in the world (Anna *et al.*, 2003). This hobby has a long history dating back to several centuries. The introduction of civil aviation after the Second World War expanded the hobby to a global industry (Tissera, 2010). Ornamental fish keeping is now emerging as an important commercial activity. Though the ornamental fish sector is small, it is a vital part of international fish trade. It contributes positively to rural development in many developing countries (FAO, 2010).

The Goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) is one of the most common and desired ornamental fish for decoration and beautification of aquariums (Ream, 1999). It is a highly demanded and sought-after aquarium fish and always commands a higher market value than other ornamental fish species (Gray, 2011). Ornamental fish keeping has developed during the last fifty years into a popular hobby because the freshwater and tropical environment have always been more easily simulated and maintained in the home aquarium than for the brackish and marine environment. The aquarium is an ideal medium for the study of biological principles of the ornamental fish according to Sudha (2012). The ornamental fish business has been flourishing, yet, Nigeria's share of the business has been small in quantity and poor in quality. An observation was made that Nigeria has a vast number of resources of tropical aquatic life and the right climate to breed (Odunaiya, 1986).

Organized trade in ornamental fish depends on an assured and adequate supply of demand, which is possible only by mass production. The induced breeding technique is a convenient way for artificial propagation and mass breeding. Induced breeding is a method of ripening fish gonad to breed in confined water using a stimulating agent and during off breeding season. A common method used for induced breeding in fish is an administration of the pituitary extract from a mammal or a fish or use of synthetic hormone (Sudha, 2012). Ovaprim is a recent synthetic hormone used at the rate of 0.5ml/kg female body weight, though research confirms lower dosages for some species (Malik *et al.*, 2014). For this type of induced breeding, a spawning ground must be provided to simulate the natural breeding environment.

Gold fish can grow to a maximum length of 22 inches (58.42cm) and a maximum weight of 9.9 pounds (4.5kg), although this is rare, few goldfish reach even half this size. The longest goldfish measured was 47.4 cm from snout to tail-fin end in Hapert, the Netherlands (Matusi, 1981). The goldfish is the highest traded variety and becoming increasingly important not only from the standpoint of the ornamental fish trade but also

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as experimental test animals because of its ability to adapt itself successfully to environmental conditions (Rana, 2002)). They are frequently reproduced in large aquariums and outdoor ponds as well. Telescopic gold is not listed on the International Union for the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN) red list. If proper management steps are not taken, this variety of gold fish may become extinct as a result of inbreeding depression or other problems (Andrew, 2002). The present study was undertaken to compare the efficiency of the synthetic hormone ovaprim with natural breeding on the spawning success of goldfish (*Carassius auratus*).

Materials and Methods

Collection and Conditioning of Brood fish

The experiment was conducted at Aquaculture Research Farm, Federal College of Fisheries and Marine Technology, Victoria Island, Lagos, Nigeria. The mature broodstock male and female goldfish species were purchased from an aquatic garden fish farm at Fadeyi, Lagos State. They were brought in an oxygen bag containing 0.5 litre of the natural water; methylene blue was added to reduce the stress of the fish, protect the female goldfish eggs and to shield them from diseases. They were then acclimated for about five hours in a holding tank.

Brood Stock Maintenance

The brood fish were stocked in circular Fiber Reinforced Plastic (FRP) tanks (1ton capacity) at 25 fish/tank. They were fed supplementary feed of (40% protein) at 5% of their body weight. The frequency of feeding was twice a day. The feeding of the broodstock lasted for 2 months.

Setting of Spawning Tanks

Fifty Litre capacity tank was each used as a holding tank for the male and female broodstocks. The tanks were cleaned, lightly laid with washed sharp sand of about 7.62cm. Nonrooted plants such as clodea weed specie were placed after the tank had been flooded with water. This was done four (4) days before the procurement of the broodstock.

Selection of Male and Female broodstock

During the selection of the spawners, sexing was done based on the differences in body shapes, females having a broader stomach, the male has pimple-like tubercles on its gill cover and pectoral fin and the female is shorter while the female also produce eggs from their genital papilla. The total length and weight of the spawners were measured with

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the aid of a metre rule and a sensitive weighing balance respectively. This was done to determine the accurate quantity of ovaprim to be injected.

Injection of the Spawners

The female fish was injected with ovaprim at the rate of 0.5ml/kg body weight of fish while the male was injected at 0.23ml/kg body weight of fish. The eggs released were weighed (in a single batch) using a sensitive weighing balance (Tesco electronic scale, model, EK4150-STR) and the total number of the eggs released was estimated (Sudha, 2012).

Induced Spawning and Fertilization

Both matured female and male fish were injected with ovaprim. The brooders were then left to spawn on their own. The hormone injected into them induced ovulation and spermiation in mature female and male gold fish respectively. The eggs developed until it reached carpool stage IV, and the sperm developed until it became potent. Then the female fish released the eggs which were immediately fertilized by the male. The time interval between administration (injection) of the hormone (ovaprim) and the time of spawning (latency period) depends on the water temperature (Table 1) (Ajani *et al.*, 2011).

Table 1. The latency period of gold fish

Temperature	Latency Period
26 ⁰ C	10 hours
27 ⁰ C	9 hours
28 ⁰ C	8 hours

The number of hatched eggs was estimated. The number of unhatched eggs was derived as the difference between the total number of eggs released and the number of hatched eggs. The percentage mortality and survival rates of the hatchlings were calculated.

Checking of Hormone efficiency

This was estimated based on parameters like fecundity, fertilization rate, hatching rate and survival rate of larvae (Sudha, 2012). Fecundity was measured by random sampling, and calculating the total number of eggs in one (1) spawning mop and multiplied with total numbers of mops in the tank. The fertilization rate of eggs was determined by randomly observing one spawning mop and counting fertilized eggs having an intact nucleus of the total eggs released. The hatching rate was calculated by comparing the

numbers of larvae and fertilized eggs. Ova diameter and egg development stages were measured using a trinocular microscope with a digital display.

Environmental Stimulation and Natural Spawning

The gold fish generally spawns with a temperature above 16⁰C. This can either happen naturally as weather pattern changes. When the pair was ready to breed, it was noticed that spawning chase occurred; the male was stayed quite close to the female and, bumping into her abdomen. The female released the eggs in batches and the male fertilized the eggs immediately by spreading milt over them. The male and female broodstocks were both removed after three (3) days. Similarly, after three days of hatching, then feeding of the young fish (fry) commenced.

Feeding of Fry

After three (3) days of hatching, the fry was fed with daphnia very early in the morning and this continued for two (2) weeks before they started taking compounded feed (0.2mm coppers). This was usually given to them very early in the morning and late in the evening.

Physico-chemical water quality parameters

During the experimental period, physico-chemical water quality parameters in the brood-stock, spawning, and larval rearing tanks were maintained at an optimum level as required for gold fish. The parameters such as Dissolved Oxygen, Temperature and pH were analyzed using multi-parameter water quality checker (model, Horiba U-22 XD) (Elezuo *et al.*, 2012).

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis of obtained data was carried out using descriptive statistics such as percentages.

Results

The Weight, Length, Average Weight and Average Length of the Brood stocks

The length and weight of the broodstocks as obtained. The male and female goldfish in the artificial breeding weighed 20 and 27g respectively while for the natural breeding the male and female weighed 20g, 25g respectively. The lengths of the male and female gold fish used for the artificial breeding were 10.20cm and 12.40cm while the length of the goldfish in the natural breeding was 10.10cm and 11.30cm respectively.

Weight and Quantity of Eggs Released

Table 2 shows the weight of eggs released during the study. For the ovaprim, the weight of eggs was 0.59g and that of the natural breeding was 0.314g. The number of eggs released was 350 for artificial breeding while that of the natural breeding was 220.

Table 2: Weight and Quantity of Eggs Released

Treatment	Sex	Weight Of eggs (g)	
OVAPRIM	Female	0.59	350
NATURAL	Female	0.314	

The Number of Eggs Fertilized, Unfertilized Eggs, and Percentage

Table 3 shows the total number of fertilized and unfertilized eggs. 225 eggs were fertilized and 125 eggs were unfertilized and the percentage fertilized and unfertilized were 64.3% and 35.7% respectively for the artificial breeding. For natural simulation, a total number of 70 eggs were fertilized and 150 eggs were unfertilized. The percentage of fertilized and unfertilized were 31.8% and 68.2% respectively.

Table 3: The Numbers of Eggs Fertilized, Numbers of Unfertilized Eggs and Percentage.

Treatment	Sex	Total No of Eggs Fertilized	No of Eggs Unfertilized	% Fertilized	% Unfertilized
OVAPRIM	Female	225	125	64.3	35.7
NATURAL	Female	70	150	31.8	68.2

Percentage Hatchability and Survival Rate of Fry

Table 4 shows the percentage hatchability for artificial and natural breeding of gold fish.

Table 4: Percentage Hatchability and Survival Rate of Fry

Treatment	No. of Hatched eggs	No. of unhatched eggs	Hatchability (%)	Survival rate (%)
Ovaprim	215	10	99.55	86.0
Natural	63	07	90.00	68.3

Physico-chemical parameters:

The Physico-chemical water quality parameters obtained during the experiment are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Physicochemical parameters of the experimental water

TREATMENT	Parameter	Optimum range
NATURAL	Temperature (°C)	28.1-28.8
	pH	6.6-7.7
	Dissolved Oxygen(mg/l)	5.4-6.7
ARTIFICIAL(OVAPRIM)	Temperature (°C)	27.0-29.5
	pH	6.5-7.4
	Dissolved Oxygen(mg/l)	5.5-5.8

Discussion

Synthetic hormones are widely used for induced breeding and have a good degree of success (Hoar and Harvey, 1979). The results of this study have shown that the number of eggs released using ovaprim was 350 eggs and 220 eggs for that of natural simulation. It was observed that the number of eggs released in artificial spawning was more than natural simulation; this is because of the efficacy and potency of ovaprim to induce oocyte maturation and ovulation of eggs (Beresford and Jobling 2004).

The percentage of fertilization in artificial was 64.3% while that of natural was 31.8%. It was observed that the percentage fertilization of that of the artificial was better than that of the natural. This is in agreement with the report of Hoar and Harvey (1979) and Legendry (1986). This is due to the potency of the ovaprim used to induce the fish.

The percentage of hatchability was 99.56% for artificial and 90.00% for natural. This shows that hatchability was high in artificial compared to the natural. This was likely due to the potency and efficacy of the hormone use in inducing the fish to maturation and

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ovulation of the oocytes and also due to the reproductive behavior of the fish (Kamonrat, 2004). The natural and artificially spawned were fed with milk powder mixed with egg yolk suspensions initially, and then an artificial diet was used after two weeks.

The growth pattern and survival showed that in artificial spawning, the percentage survival was 86.0% and 68.3% to that of natural. This might be due to difficulty by the fry to ingest artificial diets and possibly because the artificial diet was not identified by the fry. This finding has suggested that natural food organisms are the basic food of the hatchlings while artificial diet added was supplementary.

The physicochemical water parameters taken within the period of the experiment for artificial were pH (6.5-7.4), dissolved oxygen (5.5-5.8), temperature (28.1-29.5°C) while that of natural were pH (6.6-7.7), dissolved oxygen (5.4-6.7) and temperature (28.1-28.8°C). These fall within a tolerable physicochemical parameter for this species. Worynarorich *et al.* (1975) emphasized that it is important to maintain optimum temperature throughout the embryonic development and it was also observed that poor dissolved oxygen supplied at the beginning and during the latter half of embryonic development will kill the embryo. Therefore, temperature, dissolved oxygen and pH are important physico-chemical parameters that must be maintained in the incubation of the eggs.

Conclusion

This study concludes that fecundity, fertilization and hatching rate can be improved by using ovaprim as an inducement hormone. The induced breeding techniques of gravid gold fish (*Carassius auratus*) were successful than using natural hormone as shown in this work. Ovaprim, when used, could result in the economical production of fry and fingerlings for gold fish (*Carassius auratus*). This technique helps to get production all year round without any crop gap. Therefore, helps the farmers to get high production with the least input cost and better maintenance.

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